

Kinetics and Mechanism of Reduction of Tris(acetylacetonato)-cobalt(III) by Hydroxylamine and Formate in Acid Media

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The kinetics of reduction of tris(acetylacetonato)cobalt(III) by hydroxylamine and formate in aqueous acid media have been studied spectrophotometrically under different conditions. Both the complex and its protonated form are reduced by the reductants with specific rate constants k_R and $k_{H,R}$ respectively which are concurrent to the acid catalysed self reduction of the complex. From detailed analysis of the effects of acid and reductant concentrations on the rate of reduction the specific rate constants for the different paths at different temperatures and the corresponding activation parameters have been evaluated at an ionic strength of 2M. Evidence has been presented in favour of a sort of inner-sphere mechanism of reduction involving formation of a H-bonded intermediate followed by its redox transformation by a H-atom transfer mechanism.

KINETIC studies on the reduction of tris(acetylacetonato)cobalt(III) by hydrazine in acid media have been reported earlier¹. The results seem to indicate that the reduction occurs through the formation of an intermediate in which the reductant is hydrogen bonded to the oxygen of the chelated acetylacetonate ligand, followed by its transformation into the primary products of the redox reaction by a H-atom transfer process. Based on studies on the kinetics of reduction of this cobalt complex by hydroxylamine and formate in acid media and comparison of the behavior of these systems with those containing tris(oxalato)cobaltate(III) ion as the oxidant in place of Co(acac)₃, further evidence has been obtained in support of this inner-sphere type of reduction mechanism.

Experimental

Materials and Reagents :

The cobalt complex was prepared as reported earlier². Hydroxylamine hydrochloride, NH₂OH·HCl (A.R., B.D.H.) was purified by recrystallisation from aqueous ethanol. An aqueous solution of this was standardised oxidimetrically³ using KBrO₃ every time before use. Pure sodium formate (E. Merck) was recrystallised twice from water and its purity was checked oxidimetrically⁴ with KMnO₄. All other chemicals used were purified by usual methods before use.

Experimental procedure for the measurement of rate was the same as described earlier¹. Only in the case of hydroxylamine the reactions were studied in HCl-KCl media, while in the case of formate HClO₄-NaClO₄ media was used as in earlier

work¹. This was necessary in view of the unstable nature of hydroxylamine perchlorate systems. From the known basicity constants of hydroxylamine⁵ and formate⁶ it followed that the reductants were virtually completely present in their protonated forms (⁺NH₂OH and HCOOH) in the range of acid and reductant concentrations used in the experiments.

Results and Discussion

As in the case of reduction by hydrazine a three term rate law was observed in each case :

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_H[H^+] + \{k_R + k_{H,R}[H^+]\}[R]$$

where k_{obs} is the experimentally determined pseudo-first-order rate constant for the reduction of the cobalt(III) species under a particular set of conditions in presence of excess of H⁺ and the reductant, while k_H , k_R and $k_{H,R}$ are the specific rate constants for the acid catalysed self-reduction of Co(acac)₃, reduction of Co(acac)₃ by the reductant (R) and reduction of the protonated form of Co(acac)₃ by the reductant respectively (R = ⁺NH₂OH or HCOOH as the case may be). Values of these rate constants were evaluated graphically as described earlier¹ are given in Table I.

The value of the rate constant k_H obtained from experiments in perchloric acid medium in presence of formate is the same (within limits of experimental error) as that obtained earlier from the investigations using hydrazine as the reductant¹, as is to be expected.

For reduction by hydroxylamine measurements were made in aqueous HCl-KCl media because of the unstable chemical nature of hydroxylamine-

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TABLE—1. VALUES OF KINETIC PARAMETERS
(IONIC STRENGTH, 2M)

Reductant	Temp. °C	$10^4 k_H^{(Cl)}$	$10^4 k_R$	$10^4 k_{H,R}$
		$M^{-1} sec^{-1}$	$M^{-1} sec^{-1}$	$M^{-2} sec^{-1}$
Hydroxylamine	40	0.61	0.51	1.33
	50	3.55**	2.25	8.25
	60	18.05	8.00	33.43
ΔH^\ddagger , kcal mole ⁻¹ ,		35.0	27.9	32.7
ΔS^\ddagger , e.u.,		28.9	5.9	23.2
		$10^4 k_H$	$10^4 k_R$	$10^4 k_{H,R}$
		$M^{-1} sec^{-1}$	$M^{-1} sec^{-1}$	$M^{-2} sec^{-1}$
Formate	35	1.64	0.58	2.04
	40	3.93	1.83	3.78
	45	7.94	5.21	6.82
	50	16.37	14.30	11.35
ΔH^\ddagger , kcal. mole ⁻¹ ,		30.1	42.0	21.6
ΔS^\ddagger , e.u.,		16.9	53.4	-10.3

* See text.

** k_H value obtained directly from decomposition of $Co(acac)_3$ in HCl-KCl media (μ , 2M) at 50° in absence of an external reductant is $3.57 \times 10^{-5} M^{-1} sec^{-1}$. This is significantly lower than that obtained in $HClO_4-NaClO_4$ media for which the value is $17.5 \times 10^{-5} M^{-1} sec^{-1}$ at μ , 2M ($8.3 \times 10^{-5} M^{-1} sec^{-1}$, at μ , 1M)⁷. Hence, k_H in HCl-KCl media is denoted as $k_{H(Cl)}$.

perchloric acid system. In this case the k_H value obtained was significantly less than that obtained in perchloric acid media. However, this lower k_H value

Fig. 1. Isokinetic relationship: Plot of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger for different systems corresponding to different reaction paths (Ionic strength, 2M).

- : $Co(acac)_3$ -Hydrazine in perchlorate media.
- △ : $Co(acac)_3$ -Formate in perchlorate media.
- : $Co(acac)_3$ -Hydroxylamine in chloride media.
- 1 : Values corresponding to k_H .
- 2 : Values corresponding to $k_{H,R}$.
- 3 : Values corresponding to k_R .

was found to be identical to that obtained from studies on the decomposition of the complex itself in HCl-KCl media in absence of any external reductant, while the higher k_H value observed in other two cases in perchloric acid media was identical to the value observed from studies on the decomposition of the complex in $HClO_4$ media⁷ in absence of any external reductant. It is significant to note in this connection the observation of Haight, Jr., et.al.⁸ that the rate of reduction of chromium(VI) by hydroxylamine is significantly less (a factor of ca. 6 under their experimental conditions) in HCl than in $HClO_4$ media. This is obviously because $HClO_4$ is a better proton donor than HCl as is apparent from the H_0 values⁹ and the dissociation constants^{10(a,b)} of the two acids (at 25°, $\mu \approx 0$, $HClO_4$ is ca. 5.5 times stronger than HCl for solutions of the two acids of the same molar concentrations). Accordingly, the neutral substrate $Co(acac)_3$ will be more protonated in $HClO_4$ than in HCl solution of the same molar concentration of the acids, thus causing a faster overall decomposition in $HClO_4$ than in HCl of the same molar concentration, leading to a higher value of k_H in $HClO_4$ than in HCl. Hence for differentiating the experimental k_H value in HCl media it has been denoted as $k_{H(Cl)}$ in Table 1.

Fig. 2. Log-log plot for correlating the specific rates of oxidation of hydrazine, formate and hydroxylamine by tris(oxalato)cobaltate(III) ion and tris(acetylacetonato)cobalt(III). (Temp., 40°; Ionic Strength, 2M).

- A : $k = k_R$; B : $k = k_{H,R}$.
- 1 : Hydrazine, 2 : Formate,
- 3 : Hydroxylamine.

The plot of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger for all the different rate constants and the three different reductants (viz. $N_2H_8^{2+}$, $+NH_3OH$ and $HCOOH$) is linear (see Fig. 1) and this isokinetic relationship¹¹ suggests that similar mechanism of reduction operates in all the cases, i.e. for the different reaction paths and the different reaction systems studied. Similar investigations have also been made¹² on the reduction of $Co(C_2O_4)_3^{3-}$ by the three different reductants and comparison of the behaviour of the two oxidant systems also furnishes additional useful mechanistic information. Thus, it has been observed that both for k_R and $k_{H,R}$ the log-log plot of the rate constants of the two systems is linear with a slope much different from unity (see Fig.2) which is indicative¹³ of some sort of inner-sphere mechanism of the type suggested earlier.

In the case of $+NH_3OH$ and $HCOOH$ the primary oxidation products of these reductants resulting from the hydrogen atom transfer mechanism of reduction of the cobalt(III) complex¹ would be the radical species $\cdot ONH_3^+$ (or possibly $\cdot ONH_2 + H^+$)⁸ and $HCOO\cdot$ ^{14(a,b)} respectively. The former is known to decompose very rapidly⁸ forming N_2 , while the latter is likely to react with the cobalt(III) species in a fast step leading to $Co(II)$ and CO_2 .

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